

FEATURES OF FEMALE LEADERS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10246839>

Female leaders possess a unique set of qualities that are essential for effective leadership. These qualities include:

Respect: A female leader must enhance her respect through her personal qualities. It is crucial to show respect for her ideas, opinions, and actions.

Justice: A female leader should be just and proactive. It is necessary for her decisions to be fair and consistent, and to treat others with justice in their interactions.

Trust: A female leader must be trustworthy and reliable. It is important for her words and actions to be correct, and to be recognized as a trustworthy and reliable person.

Initiative: A female leader needs to be proactive and strong. It is necessary for her to be strong and proactive in achieving her goals, solving problems, and being proactive against new challenges.

Capability: A female leader must be capable and skilled. It is important for her to have the necessary skills to carry out her duties and to have a wide range of knowledge.

Appeal: A female leader must be appealing and honest. It is necessary for her to be honest, listen to the opinions of the members of the community, support them, and respond to their appeals.

How female leaders can manage both institutions and family

Managing both institutions and family can be a challenging task for female leaders, but it is definitely possible with the right strategies and support system in place. Here are some ways female leaders can manage both effectively:

Prioritize: It is important for female leaders to prioritize their tasks and responsibilities, both at work and at home. This may involve setting boundaries, delegating tasks, and making time for important family events.

Time management: Effective time management is crucial for balancing work and family life. Female leaders can use tools such as calendars, to-do lists, and scheduling to ensure that they are able to fulfill their obligations in both areas.

Communication: Open and honest communication with both their family and their colleagues is key for female leaders. They should communicate their needs and expectations clearly, and also be open to receiving support and assistance when needed.

Support system: Building a strong support system is essential for female leaders. This may involve seeking help from family members, hiring a reliable caregiver, or having a strong network of colleagues and friends who can provide assistance when needed.

Self-care: Female leaders need to prioritize their own well-being in order to effectively manage both institutions and family. This may involve setting aside time for self-care

activities, seeking professional help when needed, and maintaining a healthy work-life balance.

Flexibility: Being flexible and adaptable is important for female leaders managing both institutions and family. They should be open to adjusting their schedules and plans as needed, and be willing to make compromises when necessary.

Overall, managing both institutions and family as a female leader requires careful planning, effective communication, and a strong support system. With the right strategies in place, female leaders can successfully balance their professional and personal responsibilities.